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सुधी पाठकों,

मित्रों, भारतीय शिक्षा की त्रासदी यह है कि सत्तासीन व सत्ता से बाहर सभी राजनेता व शिक्षाविद् इसके महत्व और मानव-निर्माण के महत्व को स्वीकार तो करते हैं किन्तु इस तरफ कोई ध्यान नहीं देते- यहाँ तक कि इसकी उपेक्षा भी करते रहे हैं। आर्थिक विकास की तुलना में हम विकास की तुलना में हम विकास के इस सर्वोत्तम साधन को बहुत गौण स्थान देते रहे हैं। निःसन्देह प्राथमिक शिक्षा को राष्ट्र के विकास की नींव माना जाता है लेकिन वही क्षेत्र सबसे ज्यादा उपेक्षित रहा है। अपने ही प्रदेश में प्राथमिक विद्यालयों की हालत किसी से छुपी नहीं है। अधिकांश शिक्षकों के पद रिक्त चल रहे हैं। परिणाम यह है कि एक या दो शिक्षकों से ही पूरे विद्यालय की शिक्षा व्यवस्था चलवाई जा रही है।

गुणवत्ता की दृष्टि से तो स्थिति और भी खराब है एक ओर हम सभी के लिए शिक्षा का अभियान चला रहे हैं तो दूसरी तरफ लाखों बच्चों को केवल अक्षर ज्ञान करा देने की धोखा धड़ी कर रहे हैं और राष्ट्र की भावी पीढ़ी के भविष्य को अन्धकारमय बना रहे हैं। उच्च शिक्षा की स्थिति भी कुछ इससे अच्छी नहीं है। आखिर कब तक ऐसा चलेगा? आखिर कब तक हम भारत के पढ़े लिखे कहे जाने वाले प्रबुद्ध नागरिक भी अपनी ओर से कोई अपनी पहल न करके सरकार की तरफ निहारते रहेंगे। हम यह उम्मीद करते हैं कि आप अपने नये तार्किक विचारों को हमारे शोध प्रकाशन में प्रकाशित करते हुए शिक्षा की गुणवत्ता को बनाए रखने वाले इस यज्ञ में अपना अमूल्य योगदान देते रहेंगे।

धन्यवाद.....

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